

Synthesis of some 3d-Metal Complexes of 2,6-Diacetylpyridine(benzyl and acetone)hydrazone

D. P. SINGH^a, M. N. ANSARI^{a*} and V. B. RANA^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, S. D. College, Muzaffarnagar-251 001

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut

Manuscript received 29 February 1996, accepted 2 April 1996

2,6-Diacetylpyridine bis(benzyl and acetone)hydrazone and some 3d-metal complexes have been prepared. These complexes are five-coordinated trigonal bipyramidal. The ligand coordinates through the pyridine-N and amide-N. Formation of two chelate rings by one molecule of ligand, is a feature that undoubtedly enhances the stability of the complexes.

Derivatives of 2,6-diacetylpyridinehydrazone constitute a very important class of chelating agents. But so far, these ligands have received very little attention from the analytical point of view. The metal complexes of 2,6-diacetylpyridine based hydrazone¹ have been studied in the solid state. Chromatographic separations² of several metal ions and spectroscopic and polarographic determination³ of U^{VI} have been made with 2,6-diacetylpyridine-bis(benzylhydrazone). The reagent was used for the estimation of antimony⁴. The present communication reports the synthesis of some 3d-metal chelates of 2,6-diacetylpyridinehydrazones.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of analytical data (Tables 1 and 2), molecular formulas M(C₂₃H₂₁N₅)X₂ and M(C₁₅H₂₁N₅)X₂ (where M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}; X = Cl, Br, NO₃ or NCS) have been assigned to these chelates with ligand-A and -B respectively. Molar conductance values of the metal chelates in DMF solution indicates their non-electrolytic nature. Anions are present inside the coordination sphere as their test appears only after decomposing the complexes. Thermal properties varies from 150–300°.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES WITH 2,6-DIACETYLPIRIDINE-BIS(BENZYLHYDRAZONE) (A)*

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.
	M	X	
[Mn(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Brown)	11.17 (11.13)	14.44 (14.37)	5.82
[Mn(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Brown)	9.34 (9.43)	27.06 (27.45)	5.70
[Mn(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NO ₃) ₂] (Brown)	9.93 (10.05)	17.31 (17.57)	5.88
[Mn(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Brown)	10.37 (10.20)	11.78 (11.91)	5.74
[Fe(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Red)	11.38 (11.30)	14.64 (14.35)	5.24
[Fe(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Red)	9.64 (9.57)	27.28 (27.41)	5.25

Table-1 (contd)			
[Fe(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NO ₃) ₂] (Brown)	10.29 (10.20)	17.47 (17.54)	5.28
[Fe(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Red)	10.42 (10.35)	12.00 (11.89)	5.35
[Co(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Green)	11.73 (11.85)	14.09 (14.26)	4.30
[Co(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Brown)	10.12 (10.05)	27.12 (27.26)	4.36
[Co(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NO ₃) ₂] (Brown)	10.64 (10.71)	17.21 (17.44)	4.55
[Co(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Green)	10.92 (10.86)	11.67 (11.82)	4.40
[Ni(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Green)	11.94 (11.80)	14.48 (14.27)	2.60
[Ni(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Green)	10.17 (10.02)	27.09 (27.27)	2.40
[Ni(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NO ₃) ₂] (Green)	10.57 (10.66)	17.31 (17.45)	2.65
[Ni(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Green)	10.57 (10.82)	11.65 (11.82)	2.56
[Cu(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Brown)	12.45 (12.66)	14.05 (14.13)	1.70
[Cu(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Brown)	10.86 (10.75)	26.18 (26.05)	1.65
[Cu(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NO ₃) ₂] (Brown)	11.52 (11.44)	17.21 (17.30)	1.75
[Cu(C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Black)	11.50 (11.61)	11.85 (11.72)	1.66

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

Ir spectra : The four bands of the free ligands A and B at 1 590–1 610, 1 570–1 585, 1 450–1 490 and 1 435–1 440 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to four C=C and C=N skeletal frequencies and designated as bands I, II, III and IV of the pyridine ring respectively⁵. In the metal chelates these bands appear in the lower frequencies region indicating the coordination of pyridine-N to the metal ion. The other bands of the ligands are observed at 990 (ring breathing mode), 800 (out-of-plane C-H deformation), 610 (in-plane C-C deformation) and 410 cm⁻¹ (out-of-plane C-C deformation). Two strong bands at 790 and 735 cm⁻¹ are assign-

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES WITH 2,6-DIACETYLPIRIDINE-BIS(ACETONE HYDRAZONE) (B)*

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.
	M	X	
[Mn(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Brown)	13.48 (13.83)	17.46 (17.85)	5.80
[Mn(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Brown)	11.54 (11.30)	32.55 (32.88)	5.72
[Mn(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅ (NO ₃) ₂)] (Brown)	12.56 (12.20)	21.62 (21.31)	5.88
[Mn(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Brown)	12.80 (12.41)	14.68 (14.49)	5.72
[Fe(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Red)	14.24 (14.02)	17.62 (17.81)	5.24
[Fe(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Red)	11.22 (11.46)	33.20 (32.81)	5.25
[Fe(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NO ₃) ₂] (Red)	12.50 (12.38)	21.40 (21.27)	5.28
[Fe(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Brown)	12.85 (12.59)	14.72 (14.46)	5.36
[Co(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Green)	14.45 (14.69)	17.96 (17.67)	4.43
[Co(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Brown)	12.18 (12.02)	32.42 (32.60)	4.38
[Co(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NO ₃) ₂] (Brown)	12.66 (12.97)	21.24 (21.13)	4.53
[Co(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Green)	13.40 (13.20)	14.52 (14.36)	4.38
[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Green)	14.92 (14.63)	17.95 (17.68)	2.60
[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Green)	12.22 (11.98)	32.96 (32.62)	2.42
[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NO ₃) ₂] (Green)	13.10 (12.92)	21.40 (21.14)	2.65
[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Green)	13.26 (13.15)	14.52 (14.37)	2.56
[Cu(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Cl ₂] (Brown)	15.48 (15.65)	17.61 (17.47)	1.72
[Cu(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)Br ₂] (Brown)	12.52 (12.84)	32.10 (32.30)	1.65
[Cu(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NO ₃) ₂] (Black)	13.65 (13.84)	20.74 (20.91)	1.75
[Cu(C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅)(NCS) ₂] (Black)	14.22 (14.08)	14.04 (14.22)	1.68

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

ed to $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ and $\phi_{\text{C-C}}$ vibrations respectively⁶. In the spectra of the metal chelates, the band at $\sim 990 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is replaced by a band at $\sim 1010\text{--}1015 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Band due to $\phi_{\text{C-C}}$ splitted into two compounds appearing at 720 and 740 cm^{-1} while $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ bands appeared at $\sim 780 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as a single band. Involvement of pyridine-N in bond formation is further proved by these changes⁷. Furthermore, two ligand bands at 610 and 410 cm^{-1} underwent an upward shift by $15\text{--}20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the metal chelates, which is consistent with pyridine-N coordination to the metal atom⁷. Strong ligand bands at 1625 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 1610 cm^{-1} due to

symmetric and asymmetric $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ showed a downward shift by $15\text{--}25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the metal chelates, which is consistent with the coordination of azomethine-N to the metal atom⁸.

Nitro-complexes of the metal ions showing bands at $1530\text{--}1550$, $1260\text{--}1300$, $990\text{--}1000$ and $700\text{--}800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{NO}_2$, $\nu_{\text{asym}} \text{NO}_2$, ν_{NO} and out-of-plane NO_2 rocking respectively, suggest that NO_3 group is monodentately ($-\text{ONO}_2$) coordinated to the metal atom. This is further supported by small splittings of combination bands⁹ at $1740\text{--}1780 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and appearance of $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (nitrate) frequencies in the far-infrared spectra. Weak ir bands at 2060 , 870 , 460 in spectra of the thiocyanato complex, may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ and NCS bending vibrations respectively, which showed the presence of N-bonded thiocyanate group¹⁰.

Far-ir spectra : Some new weak bands in the spectra of the metal complexes appeared at $250\text{--}290 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggest M-N stretching (pyridine nitrogen) and are in accordance with the findings observed in the five-coordinated complexes¹¹.

In all the metal chelates, involvement of azomethine-N is evident by the appearance of new bands at $450\text{--}490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and these vibrations also substantiate five-coordinate geometry for these complexes¹². Other sharp bands appearing at $385\text{--}420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes originated from $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ of the coordinated CN group, and in conformity with the values reported for five-coordinated complexes¹³.

The chloro-complexes of these metals showing bands at $260\text{--}290 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the bromo-complexes at $210\text{--}220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to M-Cl and M-Br vibrations respectively^{5,14}. These frequencies are lower than those observed for four-coordinated complex but are higher than those for high-spin six-coordinated complexes of these metals involving both bridged and terminal halogen atoms¹⁵. The intermediate values of $\nu_{\text{M-X}}$ vibrations suggest that the present complexes are five-coordinated. Furthermore, the ratio of M-Cl/ M-Br in the present complexes falls in the range $0.87\text{--}0.81$, which is comparable to the other five-coordinated complexes reported earlier¹³.

The nitrate complexes of cobalt, nickel and copper exhibiting bands at $220\text{--}235 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M-O-NO₂) are consistent with the five-coordinate geometry. The bands of the thiocyanato complexes at ~ 290 (Cu-NCS), ~ 305 (Ni-NCS) and 270 cm^{-1} (Cu-NCS) lie in between six-coordinate and four-coordinate complexes and thus favours the five-coordinate geometry^{5,16}.

Magnetic properties and electronic spectra : The magnetic moments values of the complexes (Tables 1 and 2) suggest high-spin five-coordinate geometry and are in close agreement with the reported values¹⁷.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex of	Band cm^{-1}	Assignment
Mn^{II}	16 500–17 000	$b_1(dx^2 - y^2)$
	19 200–20 000	$a_1(d_{3z^2} - r^2)$
Fe^{II}	21 500–22 000	$e(dx_y, dyz), b_2(dx_y)$
	12 000	${}^5A - {}^5E_{(1)}$
	4 000	${}^5A - {}^5E_{(2)}$
Co^{II}	6 300	${}^4A'_2 - {}^4E''$
	13 200	${}^4A'_2 - {}^4E'$ or ${}^4A'_2 \rightarrow {}^4A'_2(P)$
	19 850	${}^4A'_2 - {}^4E''(P)$
Ni^{II}	7 300–7 500	${}^3E'_1 - {}^3E''$
	10 850–10 950	${}^3E'_1 - {}^3A''_2$
	15 450–15 550	${}^3E'_1 - {}^3A'_2$
	23 550–23 650	${}^3E'_1 - {}^3E'(P), {}^3A'_2(P)$
	27 750–27 850	C.T. band
Cu^{II}	10 300–10 420	${}^2A_1 - {}^2E'$
	13 650–13 750	${}^2A_1 - {}^2E''$
	27 000–27 250	C.T. bands

The diffuse reflectance spectral data of all the complexes recorded in DMF or pyridine and nujol are found almost similar and are given in Table 3, together with the tentative assignments for various bands based on approximate D_{3h} symmetry. For further verification of these assignments, $d-d$ spectra of other stereochemistries have been compared¹⁸. In the spectra of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, the bands at 27 000–29 000 cm^{-1} are of the charge transfer type. The calculations of various ligand field parameters is not feasible in the absence of correct energy equations. Thus on the basis of above observations, a trigonal bipyramidal structure is proposed to these complexes in which ligand molecule occupying a trigonal plane and anions being present on the axial positions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Synthesis of 2,6-diacetylpyridine-bis(benzyl and acetone)hydrazone (hereafter) designated as ligand-A and -B was carried out in two steps. (i) White needles of 2,6-diacetylpyridinedihydrazide (m.p. 180°) were obtained by mixing and stirring (2 h) a mixture of 2,6-diacetylpyridine (0.05 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 mol) in methanol (250 ml)

and crystallised from hot methanol. (ii) The dihydrazide so obtained and benzaldehyde or acetone were mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratio in methanol (200 ml) and the mixture was refluxed over a water-bath at 60–70° for 4 h. The resulting yellow solid was washed with cold water, ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The elemental analyses and ir spectral data of the compounds were consistent with their structures : 2,6-diacetylpyridine-bis(benzyl and acetone)hydrazone.

Preparation of the complexes : Ligand A or B (0.05 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (100 ml) and refluxed for 1 h. Equal amounts of equimolecular ethanolic solution of divalent Mn, Fe, Ni or Cu was then added to it followed by the addition of glacial acetic acid (1–2 drops) and the resulting solution was refluxed for 4–6 h over a water-bath. It was then concentrated to half of the volume and kept in vacuum desiccator for 3 days. The resulting crystals were washed with water and crystallised with hot ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over P_4O_{10} .

The nitro complexes were prepared from metal nitrates while for the preparation of bromo and thiocyanato complexes, metal bromide and metal thiocyanate solutions were first prepared by adding KBr or KSCN solution slowly to the ethanolic solutions of the respective metal chlorides and stirred for 3 h to separate insoluble KCl.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Princeton Applied Research 155 magnetometer using $\text{HgCo}(\text{CNS})_4$ as calibrant. Ir (KBr) and far-ir (nujol) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1600 FTIR spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Carl-Zeiss Specord spectrophotometer. Conductivity was measured on a Toshniwal CL 01/01 conductivity bridge and molecular weights by Backmann's cryoscopic method in solvents depending upon the solubility of the complexes.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the grant of a Teachers Fellowship to one of them (D.P.).

References

1. C. PELIZZI, G. PELIZZI and F. VITALI, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1986, **11**, 401; *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1987, 177.
2. V. MARK, J. MAIN and S. FRITZ, *Anal. Chem.*, 1989, **61**, 1272; A. CASOLI, A. MANGIA and G. PREDIERIA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1985, **57**, 561.
3. A. CASOLI, A. MANGIA, G. MORI and G. PREDIERIA, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 1986, **186**, 283.
4. M. CARCIA-VARGES, C. BELEZON, M. MIILA and J. A. P. BUSTAMANTE, *Analyst*, 1985, **110**, 51.
5. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectroscopy of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 2nd. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.

6. W. G. GILBERT, L. T. TAYLOR and J. G. DILLARD, *J. Am. Chem Soc.*, 1973, **75**, 2477; S. P. SINHA, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1964, **20**, 879.
7. N. S. GILL, R. H. NUTTAL, D. E. SCAEFE and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **79**, 18; N. S. GILL and H. J. KINGDON, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1966, **19**, 2197.
8. J. A. FANIRAN, K. S. PATEL and J. C. BAILAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl Chem* , 1974, **36**, 1545.
9. A. N. P. LEVER, E. MANTOVANI and B. S. RAMASAWAMY, *Can J. Chem.*, 1971, **49**, 1957.
10. G. B. AITKEN and G. P. MC QUILLAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 2637.
11. A. B. P. LEVER, M. KEETON and B. S. RAMASAWAMY, *Spectrochim Acta, Part A*, 1970, **26**, 2173; T. SHIMANOUCI and T. NAKAGAWA, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **18**, 89.
12. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal Lingand and Related Vibration", Arnold, London, 1967; A. B. P. LEVER and E. MANTOVANI, *Inorg. Chum Acta*, 1971, **5**, 429.
13. M. KEETON and A. B. P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 47.
14. B. J. HATHAWAY and D. E. BILLING, *Chem Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 143.
15. FERRARO, "Low Frequency Vibrations of Inorganic Coordination Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1971.
16. A. B. P. LEVER, D. A. BALDWIN and R. Y. PARISH *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 107.
17. L. SACCONI *J. Chem Soc. (A)*, 1970, 248; A. T. PHILLIPS, W. MASUREK and A. T. CASEY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, **24**, 501; L. SACCONI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **8**, 351.
18. J. S. WOOD, *Prog. Inorg. Chem* , 1972, **16**, 227.